

I AM ONEHEALTH CITIZEN SCIENCE INITIATIVE

A Pilot Project Report

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OVERVIEW

The I Am One Health initiative, developed by the echo network in collaboration with the Bengaluru Science and Technology Cluster (BeST), empowered communities to actively participate in dengue prevention efforts. The project aimed to raise awareness about dengue prevention, train students in One Health concepts and research, and engage residents in co-creating data-driven solutions. The primary objective was to leverage the power of local residents in a city-wide citizen science initiative that provided direct information on hyperlocal environmental conditions for a future surveillance dashboard. At the same time, it mobilized a citywide effort to mitigate water stagnation and contamination issues.

2024 witnessed an alarming rise in dengue cases worldwide, and experts point to human impacts on our environment as major factors increasing disease risk. Standing water in waste piles, broken pipes, construction sites, and even garden pots can serve as breeding grounds for mosquitoes who can transmit dengue. Citizen scientists are ideally placed to participate in real-time, hyperlocal data and information gathering for better city planning and decision-making for public health.

By addressing this issue through community involvement, this initiative seeks to empower the public and spread awareness of these issues for more resilient and healthier cities. Residents must be empowered to actively participate in observation, data collection, and decision-making to help prevent and monitor disease risks. Further, student ambassadors can be trained to inform neighbors and peers about One Health and the role of environmental and animal health in human health outcomes. To address these goals, we need to establish accessible curricula and easy-to-use digital tools that allow students and residents to easily educate themselves and others and participate in the research process.

Do you know YOU have the power to make a real difference in the fight against dengue fever!

WhatsApp +91 84969 37347
to report standing water

MAJOR OBJECTIVES

1. **City-wide awareness campaign** - Collaborate with local experts and practitioners for raising awareness of OneHealth and Dengue
2. **Empower student ambassadors** - Train student ambassadors across Bangalore to champion ecological and environmental knowledge for dengue modelling and surveillance
3. **Leverage local expertise** - Partner with local experts and practitioners to develop a citizen science education module
4. **Real-time Disease Surveillance** - Develop a system for citizen-collected data to feed directly into surveillance dashboards and models
5. **Mass action for reporting on standing water** - Empower citizens to identify and report potential sources of contamination See it. Say it. Dump it.

HOW IT WORKED

Focusing on high school students and residents across Bengaluru, India, the initiative equipped participants with the necessary training and tools to collect hyperlocal environmental data critical to understanding the spread of dengue. To do this, we created a dedicated website, <https://www.iamone.health>, featuring relevant explanatory content and videos in English and Kannada on dengue, one health, and citizen science. In addition, a training module was created for masters-level student trainers and local teachers to engage students in the citizen science initiative. Emphasizing the "train the trainers" model, both trainer categories participated in workshops to assess the curriculum and discuss how to train students and residents in the city. The module can be accessed at: <https://www.iamone.health/citizen-science/learning-module-en-only>.

To address the need for accessible, efficient, and accurate data collection and storage, we tested two platforms: Epicollect5 and a customized WhatsApp chatbot. Epicollect5 is a commonly used citizen science tool designed to gather detailed data. In contrast, the WhatsApp chatbot is an accessible and multilingual tool for reporting simple information via a mobile phone app widely used in India.

In assessing both platforms, we asked users several questions regarding data input, including sharing the GPS location and pictures of standing water, identifying the type of infrastructure where the water was found, and providing a basic description of the standing water. We also enquired about the standing water's duration to ascertain if it could serve as a breeding site for mosquitoes (approximately 8-10 days from egg to adult). Through constant participant feedback, we streamlined our approach by consolidating and modifying the data collection process. The WhatsApp chatbot was found to be more accessible for participants and was ultimately selected and refined for further use. Both platforms can be accessed through the following links:

Epicollect5: <https://five.epicollect.net/project/i-am-onehealth>

WhatsApp chatbot: <https://wa.me/918496937347?text=Hi>

To spread awareness of the initiative across the city, we also held a one-day festival with several local one health-related organizations at the Visvesvaraya Industrial and Technological Museum in Bengaluru, attended by over 600 local residents. We also participated in exposure workshops for various schools across the city and presented a talk at the Ramaiah University of Applied Sciences. During these events, we explained the role of citizen science, demonstrated our website, learning module, and tools, and guided attendees in using the tools with their mobile phones.

MAJOR OUTCOMES

1. **I Am OneHealth Festival** - An engaging awareness drive with over 600 participants from local schools, health practitioners, and researchers to raise awareness of OneHealth and Dengue.

2. **Learning Module** - A curriculum tool educate students and citizens on One Health, dengue, and citizen science.

3. **Citizen Science** - A digital platform co-created with champion citizens and over 90 students from 6 schools for citizen-led research on hyperlocal environmental data.

4. **Data Point Generation** - A wide-scale citywide effort to assess, monitor, and remove dengue breeding sites with over 400 data points across the city.

Over 90 high school students were trained across six schools, supported by organizations like Parikrma Humanity Foundation and CII Young Indians, to use Epicollect platform and the WhatsApp chatbot for collecting data points on standing water citywide.

the echo network created a visual documentary of the work done as part of this unique Citizen Science program designed to empower high school students and residents of Bengaluru to join scientists, government officials, doctors, and organizations to help fight dengue.

IMPACT

The I Am One Health initiative raised awareness and empowered communities in Bengaluru through extensive outreach, training, and citizen engagement. Over 90 high school students were trained across six schools, supported by teachers and volunteers from organizations like Parikrma Humanity Foundation and CII Young Indians. Using the Epicollect platform and, ultimately, the WhatsApp chatbot, the program collected roughly 400 data points on standing water citywide, contributing to a planned vulnerability index and a future dashboard for dengue prevention. After data cleaning and collation, the data was shared with scientists collaborating on the broader project and was integrated with Google Maps to visually represent the collaborative efforts. The location and details of the sites for all data points are presented via the link below:

<https://www.iamone.health/map>

The initiative featured an educational series, a chatbot, a festival, workshops, conference talks, learning modules and bilingual information, and a dedicated website, ensuring broad accessibility.

This process was documented in a video at

[https://www.youtube.com/watch?](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GcMDAbbz2_o)

[v=GcMDAbbz2_o](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GcMDAbbz2_o)

ROAD AHEAD

This pilot study provided hyperlocalized information, highlighted as a critical gap by several one health experts. Using citizen science approaches and digital tools, participants documented factors such as water stagnation, which can serve as potential mosquito breeding grounds. As dengue and other zoonotic diseases are global problems, this effort has the potential to scale beyond one city. Collaborative efforts with government bodies can help scale the efforts beyond conventional boundaries.

In the future, we intend to operationalize our developed chatbot through a recent MoU with Tata Consultancy Services Tech4Hope program and enhance its functionality by integrating additional climatic factors such as image analysis, current air pollution levels, temperature, humidity, rainfall, altitude, and current wind speed during observation. We are also in the process of integrating geographical and environmental indicators like green cover (e.g., NDVI), and blue cover (e.g., NDWI), as well as population density, and mobility information. Together, these enhancements can provide a comprehensive, data-driven approach for improved environmental monitoring and disease prevention. With these additions, we anticipate that this tool can be used widely by several municipalities. We welcome the opportunity to continue to collaborate with BeST and associated organizations to scale this effort in Karnataka and nationwide.

We also found that sustained and clear media outreach is necessary to encourage participation and action. While students engaged in sustained participation through guidance from teachers and peer mentors, residents sporadically contributed when targeted through mass and social media channels. Further, residents were hesitant to take action to remove the standing water, suggesting a specific need for awareness of the safety and health issues of individual action. To encourage resident action, such additions can be made to the curriculum.

CONCLUSION

This effort increased capacities, raised awareness of the impacts of climate and environment on health, and provided increased community partnership between government and citizens. By integrating hyperlocal data with broader datasets—including disease prevalence, mosquito abundance, and community awareness—gathered through collaborative partnerships, the program aims to develop a comprehensive vulnerability index for the city. This index will help identify high-risk areas, enabling targeted interventions. At the same time, the initiative fosters awareness of water stagnation and contamination, encouraging proactive efforts to mitigate these issues. Through students' active participation as ambassadors and local trainers' guidance, the program inspired collective action and raised awareness to combat the spread of dengue in Bengaluru.

(L-R) Nour Al-Bakaa, TCS, Shannon Olsson, Founder & Global Director the echo network, Suneeta Ijari, TCS and Vikram Sharma, Country Head TCS in Denmark

I Am OneHealth
Initiative

**Thank You for
Being a Dengue Warrior!**